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From Funding to Financing: Complementary Pathways, Refugee Finance and the Emergence of the Refugee Entrepreneur

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ABSTRACT

As part of the implementation of the Comprehensive Refugee Response Framework and the Global Compact on Refugees we are witnessing the promotion of refugee responses aimed at creating an enabling environment for sustainable investments. This marks a paradigmatic shift “from funding to financing” which sees the role of financial markets becoming central to the way in which refugee responses are managed. By theorizing the link between the emergence of refugee finance and the simultaneous development of complementary pathways in the EU, this article assesses their wider implications for international refugee protection, as well as for the conceptualization of refugeehood more broadly.

KEYWORDS

Refugee finance; complementary pathways; international protection; social sustainable investment; Global Compact on Refugees

1. Introduction

Migration control policies have a well-established pedigree at both EU and member state level and are certainly not a new phenomenon (Parsons & Smeeding, 2006). Following the 2015 long summer of migration (Davitti, 2018; Römhild et al., 2017), however, we have witnessed an intensification and consolidation of already existing trends toward externalization and the adoption of deterrence measures to limit spontaneous refugee arrivals. Carrier sanctions, visa requirements and, more recently, offshore processing attempts such as the Italy-Albania Migration Protocol of November 2023 (Veshi et al., 2024) are only some of the examples of existing deterrence measures being pursued in Europe (Tan, 2022) and beyond (Dehm, 2020).

In response to these trends, growing attention has been paid to the development of new legal pathways to protection—additional to resettlement—labeled as “complementary pathways.” Simultaneously, the last decade has also seen a change in the way in which multilateral actors fund humanitarian responses to refugee movements, with a clear shift “from funding to financing” that sees financial actors and instruments acquiring a central role and substantially replacing aid funding. As examined in this article, both complementary pathways and refugee finance are at an early stage of operationalization. Thus, whilst it would be premature perhaps to provide any conclusive evaluation on the benefits and/or drawbacks of the ways in which they interact, in this article we outline how they are both promoted and supported by a significant policy and governance architecture that will likely remain for the years to come. By obtaining a clearer understanding of the policy and governance architecture, it is possible to reflect on some concerns related to the situations of precarity and non-durability that characterize the operational spaces of both phenomena. Through a closer examination of current policy trends at EU level, we submit that despite the opportunities and potentials which complementary pathways and

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refugee finance represent in terms of strengthening international protection, they however risk simultaneously accelerating the end of spontaneous arrivals by transforming themselves into additional migration control tools, instrumental to the containment and externalization of migration.

As part of the implementation of the Comprehensive Refugee Response Framework (CRRF) and of the Global Compact on Refugees (GCR), we see a push for policies aimed at encouraging refugee self-reliance as well as at creating a conducive environment for sustainable investment. This aim could of course also contribute to the strengthening of international protection, but such a simultaneous outcome cannot be assumed nor be expected to flow automatically from an increased reliance on refugee finance and complementary pathways. CRRF's objectives go hand in hand with the increased adoption of temporary solutions, which prioritize *local* rather than *durable* protection. This approach is arguably fueled by current trends at international level which promote the notion of "protection elsewhere" (Foster, 2007), originally advanced by Australia and the United States but also increasingly now favored by the EU and its member states (Dastyari et al., 2022; Ghezelbash, 2018; Mountz, 2020; Scott FitzGerald, 2019; Tan, 2023). Due to a general desire to curtail access to territorial asylum, resettlement quotas in EU member states now serve the needs of only a small fraction of refugees in need of international protection and, as the initial acceptance of Ukrainian refugees has shown, EU states prefer refugees with racial and religious profiles similar to that of their own population (UNHCR, 2022b). Complementary pathways, also, are often portrayed as the only alternative for people in need in protection who do not qualify for resettlement.

This, however, fundamentally alters the protection space and, in our view, risks creating a new spectrum of refugeehood (Ilcan & Rygiel, 2015; Scott-Smith, 2016) with the "hyper vulnerable" refugee on the one end of the spectrum, considered as the only category eligible for resettlement and at the other end of the spectrum the "refugee entrepreneur" (Davitti & Vankova, 2024). The latter emerges from a longstanding emphasis on the self-reliant refugee (Betts et al., 2012; Easton-Calabria & Omata, 2018; Turner, 2020) capable of transforming all at once into a businessperson, migrant worker or student in order to avail of the new complementary pathways rather than requiring humanitarian support or demanding their rights be protected, respected and fulfilled (ibid, Turner, 2020). Spontaneous refugees form the squeezed middle section of this new spectrum of refugeehood, for those who do not fulfill the requirements of either hypervulnerability or entrepreneurship and are left instead with little or no alternative for obtaining protection (ibid).

Across this new spectrum of protection, we see numerous challenges related to the precariousness and non-durability of refugee protection. Achieving durable solutions for the refugee entrepreneur will depend on their qualifications, skills and opportunities to access permanent residence status in the host EU member state (Vankova, 2022, Vankova, 2023). And the hyper-vulnerable refugees who benefited from resettlement options, or those who obtained temporary protection or any other humanitarian status on the basis of complementary pathways, are now increasingly at risk of being returned to their country of origin, not least due to a growing trend toward the adoption of cessation measures (Tan, 2021). In line with changes in the conceptualization of protection and durable solutions, we see how EU member states are increasingly stepping away from the concept of local integration toward the idea of "enforced" cessation of refugee status, where refugees are sent back to their country of origin when the situation there is considered to have improved (Schultz, 2021). How this "improvement" is measured remains unclear and is often arbitrary, since legally a refugee can only go back to their country of origin on a voluntary basis and where the well-founded fear of persecution no longer persists (Cassarino, 2020; Fakhoury & Stel, 2022; Ihlamur-Öner, 2022). In addition, a whole set of rights would also militate in favor of local integration when a refugee has established herself in the host-country (Edwards, 2005).

Against this backdrop of enforced cessation, involuntary returns and preference for temporary protection, refugee finance promotes itself as an ideal set of financial instruments to scale up

and mobilize private capital in order to accelerate short-term protection measures. Given the dearth of funding currently available for refugee responses, humanitarian organizations appear keen to embrace refugee finance, without critically evaluating whether and how this may be changing the nature of international protection at the macro-level. In certain circumstances, complementary pathways can and do sometimes offer feasible solutions for refugees in protracted situations who do not qualify for the limited resettlement places available (Vankova, 2022). It is valid however to ask what happens to durable solutions and international protection when the focus of refugee responses moves toward the creation of an enabling environment for sustainable investors and policies aimed at supporting refugees' self-reliance (Davitti, 2022), including the facilitation of complementary pathways.

To address these questions, the article adopts a case study methodology allowing to empirically study the development and (where possible) the implementation of impact bonds that serve as design-stage grants from the perspective of an EU Member State—Finland—and a country of first asylum, namely Jordan. As complementary pathways' aims go beyond simply providing access to a territory and seek also to achieve certain integration outcomes, the article focuses on employment integration initiatives as part of the pilots funded. Even if not directly connecting complementary pathways and refugee finance, these pilots are useful to trace the broader implications for international protection and to illustrate the ways in which both complementary pathways and refugee finance may have unexpected consequences and ultimately delineate a different understanding of refugeehood and durable solutions.

The article is structured as follows: in [sections 1 and 2](#) we introduce, respectively, the key features of refugee finance and complementary pathways, to provide a backdrop to their further development. In [section 3](#), we trace the simultaneous emergence of these two phenomena, showing how their convergence is not accidental but firmly established in a complex policy architecture built around the GCR and the CRRF (Davitti, 2022). Through a closer reading of these two documents, we can see how they prioritize and promote both complementary pathways and refugee finance, presenting them as innovative “win-win” solutions to achieve self-reliance and burden sharing. In [section 4](#), to better examine how refugee finance operates in practice, we focus on two case studies, one of a development impact bond in Jordan and one of a social impact bond in Finland. [Section 5](#) concludes.

1. Refugee finance, the key to the shift “from funding to financing” in international protection

In order to provide a backdrop to examine the policy convergence between refugee finance and complementary pathways, we explain in this section, at least in general terms, what refugee finance is. As a result of the decline in aid from traditional bilateral and multilateral donors, refugee finance emerged as an attractive funding paradigm, despite the dearth of information and in-depth research on the topic. The term “refugee finance” refers to new financial instruments, from refugee bonds to technical assistance funds, aimed at mobilizing private capital to achieve social impact objectives, in this case, refugee protection. The appeal of refugee finance revolves around the need to put in place funding modalities capable of bridging the shift from short-term humanitarian assistance to longer-term development programming (Zetter, 2021). According to its proponents—mainly international organizations, international financial institutions, financial intermediaries and states—refugee finance promises to ensure refugees' resilience and self-reliance, whilst at the same time supporting the economic development of the host communities.

There are four main financial instruments relevant to our discussion on refugee finance. First, concessional loans, i.e. loans usually made to a borrower by a government, or in this context also by philanthropic investors, at a lower rate compared to the market rate. Concessional loans usually consist of a component which is at a market rate and one that is at a discounted rate, such as the loans issued by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD).

Second, technical assistance funds, aimed at supporting the initial stages of a business (Kluge et al., 2018). They are also considered ecosystem builders since they are aimed at facilitating refugee entrepreneurship, subsequent investment and integration (Kluge et al., 2018). These technical assistance funds are seen as crucial to ensuring a base for further investment and the creation of other financial mechanisms.

Third, guarantees and risk insurance, whereby International Financial Institutions, governments and/or philanthropic investors provide guarantees or insurance priced below market rates. Examples of this type of insurance are those offered for natural disasters, also called parametric insurance, which in theory pays out before a crisis escalates, for instance at the early stages of a humanitarian emergency or a pandemic (Erikson, 2015; Clarke, 2020). The fourth and final group of financial instruments relates to design-stage grants, which are usually allocated to create an enabling environment for so-called refugee resilience, for instance loans conditional to the passing of legislation which would allow refugees to work or improve the treatment of women in the host-country. This is how, for instance, the Jordan and Lebanon Compacts were established under the CRRF (Howden et al., 2017).

Whilst many scholars and practitioners have already critiqued the notions of self-reliance and burden sharing and shown how they have been used to foreground policies of deterrence and externalization (Easton-Calabria, 2022; Krause & Schmidt, 2020), the emergence of refugee finance and of its relationship with complementary pathways adds a layer of complexity by creating a reliance on volatile financial markets. As we further discuss in this article, this could in turn increase the precarity and temporariness of protection (Krause & Schmidt, 2020), and ultimately transform the nature of durable solutions and international protection.

In the next section, we introduce the key features of complementary pathways, before turning to examine the way in which their emergence converged with the rise of refugee finance.

2. In search of legal entry options: Understanding complementary pathways

Introduced initially as “legal pathways for admission” by the 2016 New York Declaration (UNGA, 2016a), and later labeled as “complementary pathways” by the CRRF (paragraphs 10 and 14(a)), these policy tools aim to provide legal entry options to third countries for people in need of protection outside the traditional asylum system and in addition to the limited and largely inaccessible resettlement places (de Boer & Zieck, 2020; Garnier et al., 2018). They gained prominence as a response to the tragedies in the aftermath of the Arab spring (Vankova, 2022), even though many such legal pathways had already been developed before that (van Selm, 2023). Promoting and expanding such pathways have also become an integral part of the Global Compacts and the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum.

Complementary pathways comprise of existing immigration entry channels, such as those based on labor, education and family reunification grounds which are made accessible for people in need of protection. They also cover humanitarian admission programmes, including community sponsorship and humanitarian corridors. Despite criticism that complementary pathways do not focus on “what happens after the movement” (Stoyanova, 2023), their aim is often also to ensure long-term integration prospects for their beneficiaries (UNHCR, 2022a). Therefore, their development and implementation needs to be assessed with potential integration outcomes in mind. In line with this, in this article we look at refugee labor mobility and education-based pathways whilst also considering employment integration initiatives.

Refugee mobility pilot projects have been developed worldwide over the past few years with Canada as frontrunner in this regard with the largest Economic Mobility Pathways Project (UNHCR, 2022b), followed by the UK and Australia (Katsiaticas et al., 2023). At the time of writing there are two EU pilot projects covering the development of refugee labor mobility pathways—one explicitly focusing on employment pathways and the other focusing on education pathways with a community sponsorship component (Katsiaticas et al., 2023). Education pathways, offering mainly scholarships and other types of financial support to refugee students, have

also been introduced in different countries in cooperation with universities, NGOs, public institutions, and private donor organizations (Sabchev et al., 2023).

As van Selm emphasizes, the initial impetus to develop such pathways into the EU resulted merely in “a drop in the ocean compared to the number of displaced persons fleeing conflict in Syria” (van Selm, 2023). Even though pilot projects and initiatives are increasing the result of the Global Compacts, the main outstanding issue with complementary pathways remains their scalability (Doyle & Peltz, 2020; Vankova, 2022, Vankova, 2023). For instance, the UNHCR’s initial Three-Year Strategy report demonstrates that there are still challenges in this regard, as the number of arrivals over the period 2019–2021 did not meet the targets initially set (UNHCR, 2022b). Scalability would depend on the part of governments to assess these pilots positively and integrate them into their immigration systems in order for refugees to benefit from such pathways.

Another important aspect in the implementation of such complementary pathways includes questions concerning funding, durability and potential adverse effects at the asylum system and the individual protection needs level (van Selm, 2023). A concern related to the implementation of such pathways is how they fit into the bigger “asylum picture.” The promotion and development of complementary pathways brings with it both restrictions to spontaneous asylum applications and a subsequent externalization of asylum processing (van Harten, 2023; van Selm, 2023). Other implementation challenges are related to the durability of such pathways and to the fact that it is impossible to return those who benefit from complementary pathways. Therefore, another significant question related to skill-based pathways is whether they can offer some sort of long-term integration options by providing easier access to permanent residence so as to ensure durable solutions (Vankova, 2022, Vankova, 2023). Since the asylum and migration systems continue to exist in separate spheres, the reliance on refugee law standards can be triggered only after such beneficiaries apply for asylum, yet without a guaranteed prospect of obtaining a secure status (Vankova, 2022).

The link between resettlement, complementary pathways and refugee finance becomes apparent when we look at funding streams. The use of financial instruments, in fact, is promoted by the European Commission as part of its Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF, 2023) and the UNHCR (2022c), since they both explicitly link the expansion of resettlement programmes to innovative financing models and refer to public-private partnerships, aimed at the “matching of government resources with private funds” (UNHCR, 2022c). Similarly, innovative financing models are expected “to cover the upfront cost of integration” when it comes to education pathways, again by using models relying on matching government resources with private funds (UNHCR, 2022c). Funding education pathways through social-impact bonds has also been outlined as a policy option by a report of the University of Ottawa’s Refugee Hub (Sabchev et al., 2023). It is therefore clear that there is a growing relationship between complementary pathways and refugee finance which deserves closer attention since the ways in which complementary pathways are financed or funded ultimately has an impact on their implementation outcomes. The examination of this relationship is the focus of the next section, where we trace the governance architecture both enabling and strengthening these policies.

3. Tracing convergence between complementary pathways and refugee finance: The Global Compact on Refugees and the Comprehensive Refugee Response Framework

The emergence of complementary pathways may, at first sight, appear disconnected from the parallel rise of refugee finance. As we explain in this section, however, these two phenomena have not developed in isolation and are part of a broader governance architecture which may fundamentally change the way international protection is conceptualized and approached, both in theory and in practice. The push for restructuring the refugee governance regime is linked to broader transformations which have occurred, primarily, at the level of institutional structure. Already with Agenda 2030 and the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals in 2015

(UNGA, 2015), the international community embraced the notion of multi-stakeholder partnerships (Erdem Türkelli, 2021) as a way to attract private capital to realize development objectives. A similar approach also characterized the 2015 debates around the Grand Bargain, a humanitarian agenda officially launched at the 2016 World Humanitarian Summit, which had, amongst its main objectives, a commitment to galvanize and foster “innovative partnerships with the private sector” (IASC, 2016). In the specific context of responses to displacement, this push for “innovative partnerships” was promoted by the 2016 United Nations High-Level Meeting on Addressing Large Movements of Refugees and Migrants as part of its New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants (UNGA, 2016a). A key element of the New York Declaration, in fact, is the establishment, in Annex I, of the CRRF as a vision of “burden- and responsibility-sharing” (UNGA, 2016a). The approach of the New York Declaration and the statement of the 2016 World Humanitarian Forum, and thus implicitly the commitments of the Grand Bargain, were later officially adopted for practical implementation by the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA) in its 2017 policy paper “New Way of Working” (UNOCHA, 2017). In this latter document, UNOCHA acknowledged “a growing consensus for a new and comprehensive approach to meet the challenges of displacement that goes beyond addressing immediate humanitarian needs” (ibid). This approach is predicated upon the need to bridge the gap between humanitarian and development responses and to “leverage international financial institutions and the private sector, together with national governments” (ibid). These needs were ultimately confirmed in 2018, both conceptually and operationally, with the adoption of the GCR (UNGA, 2018b) and the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration (UNGA, 2018a).

It is important to note, for the purposes of this article, that the transformation of the institutional structure underpinning and enabling refugee finance developed in parallel to the escalating political concerns over the so-called European refugee “crisis” (Davitti, 2018; De Genova, 2017) and “the perceived negative socio-economic impacts of the increasingly spontaneous global movement of people including refugees” (Zetter, 2021). Both 2018 Global Compacts take as their starting point the “reinforcement of protection” and the active promotion of development-led approaches to refugee displacement. As evidenced in this article, however, an increased focus on development-led approaches might not necessarily lead to the desired “reinforcement of protection”, unless it is ensured that “protection” still means protection from persecution and political exclusion (Aleinikoff & Owen, 2022; Long, 2013). As mentioned above, these development-led approaches are largely based on the multi-stakeholder governance model promoted with the 2015 Grand Bargain which envisaged an increased collaboration with state donors, multilateral agencies and private stakeholders (Zetter, 2021).

A key aspect of the 2018 Global Compacts, not usually examined in legal discussions on these two policy documents, is that they endorsed and consolidated specific modalities of responsibility-sharing which included the financial modalities elaborated upon in the Grand Bargain. Thus, in order to fully understand the institutional transformation pertaining to the reform of refugee governance, we need to understand what happened in 2015, and look at the responsibility-sharing recommendations that the Grand Bargain put forward. According to the 2017 briefing paper “The Grand Bargain: Everything you Need to Know”, the negotiators of the Grand Bargain (also known as “Sherpas”) were mainly international donor states and international agencies (World Humanitarian Summit, 2016). The Sherpas met four times between February and May 2016 and developed commitments for an overhaul of the humanitarian response system. Turkey, the UAE, and the WHO initially declined to sign the Grand Bargain, while some states (e.g. Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Italy, Luxembourg, and Poland) and international agencies (e.g. UNFPA and UN Women) that were not involved in the negotiations endorsed it before its presentation at the 2016 World Humanitarian Summit.

The latter also included 350 representatives of the private sector. These actors introduced important changes at the operational level which in turn affected the modalities of funding made available to refugee responses, enabling the shift “from funding to financing” key to the

emergence of refugee finance. There are two key complementary documents that can help us to understand the shift “from funding to financing” triggered by the Grand Bargain: the 2016 report of the UN Secretary General for the World Humanitarian Summit, entitled “One Humanity: Shared Responsibility” (UNGA, 2016b); and the report to the UN Secretary General by the High-Level Panel on Humanitarian Financing (High-Level Panel on Humanitarian Financing, 2016). Invoking the notion of shared responsibility to confront the challenges faced by humanity, the Secretary General’s report introduced a “whole of society” approach in which the private sector was presented as an essential actor in transcending the humanitarian-development divide and, ultimately, in ensuring what the international community saw as a fundamental shift from funding individual projects to financing collective outcomes aimed at reducing needs and vulnerability (UNGA, 2016b).

This shift introduced, in turn, a diversity of actors who were identified as having the necessary competitive advantage to deliver on these collective outcomes through a broad range of financing instruments such as impact bonds, concessional loans, technical assistance funds and guarantees (ibid). In a similar vein, the High-Level Panel on Humanitarian Financing had in fact recommended relying on innovative financing for humanitarian action, and shifting “some of the funding burden to modes of public-private portfolio investments” (High-Level Panel on Humanitarian Financing, 2016) such as social impact bonds. These financial instruments were also suggested as necessary tools to “develop a stronger result-based culture” amongst humanitarian actors (ibid).

This emphasis on innovative financing created the basis for a *de facto* fully fledged re-orientation toward market-based responses to situations of protracted displacement, presented as a move away from emergency responses and toward renewed efforts to transcend the humanitarian-development divide. More specifically to the emergence of refugee finance, and for the purposes of this article, the High-Level Panel on Humanitarian Financing recommended, amongst other things, to promote development finance in protracted crises and, wherever possible, move to joint humanitarian-development financial programming (Davitti, 2022). Whilst before 2015 most of the humanitarian community focused on the need to fund bottom-up approaches and empower local actors in humanitarian response, the Grand Bargain spearheaded a series of reforms that not only irreversibly changed the nature of emergency funding, but also consolidated the international community’s intention to complete the shift “from funding to financing.” As discussed so far in this article, it is important that we do not conceive of the Grand Bargain in isolation, but rather that we see it as an acceleration toward this financing transformation, reinforced by Agenda 2030 and the Sustainable Development Goals, in particular SDG 17 on Partnerships for the Goals (Davitti, 2022).

In turn, the language of burden and responsibility sharing, first introduced by Agenda 2030 and by the Grand Bargain, was reproduced in the 2016 New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants and in its CRRF. Paragraph 2 of the CRRF indeed embraces the multi-stakeholder approach encouraged in preceding reports, and places international financial institutions and private sector actors amongst key stakeholders in providing refugee responses, alongside national and local authorities, international and regional organizations, regional coordination and partnership mechanisms, and civil society partners (including faith-based organizations, academia, media and the refugees themselves).

Amongst the measures to support the immediate and ongoing needs of refugees, paragraph 6 of the CRRF establishes a cooperation between states, multilateral donors and private sector partners to mobilize financial and other resources to cover the humanitarian needs identified in the CRRF, not least by extending “the finance lending schemes that exist for developing countries to middle-income countries hosting large numbers of refugees, bearing in mind the economic and social costs to those countries” (UNGA, 2016a, para. 6(c)). The extension of finance lending schemes to middle-income countries hosting large number of refugees is what has *de facto* enabled, for instance, the allocation of concessional loans for states located in the proximity of “refugee-producing” areas.

At the same time, the CRRF embodies the emergence of a renewed focus on refugee resilience and self-reliance and a move away from traditional durable solutions for international protection—understood as local integration, resettlement and voluntary return—to a focus on “third-country solutions” and “returns” (Cassarino, 2019, 2020). Namely, the four stated objectives of the CRRF are to:

- Ease the pressure on host countries and communities;
- Enhance refugee self-reliance;
- Expand access to third-country solutions;
- Support conditions in countries of origin for return in safety and dignity.

These objectives introduce some changes which at first sight may appear minor but which are in fact quite significant in terms of how international protection is redesigned. As mentioned earlier in this article, we see them as are part of a broader transformation which ultimately crystallized in 2018 with the GCR. The framework introduced by the GCR, in fact, builds on the notion of burden- and responsibility-sharing, introduced with the Grand Bargain, to promote “the mobilization of timely, predictable, adequate and sustainable public and private funding” (UNGA, 2018b, para 32) for the successful implementation of the compact itself. The premise of the approach to refugee governance and refugee finance embraced by the GCR is that financing efforts should be expanded beyond traditional donors to encompass and maximize private sector contributions. This, in turn, would include

policy measures and de-risking arrangements; opportunities for private sector investment, infrastructure strengthening and job creation in contexts where the business climate is enabling; development of innovative technology, including renewable energy, particularly with a view to closing the technology gap and supporting capacity in developing and least developed refugee-hosting countries; and *greater access to financial products* and information services for refugees and host communities (UNGA, 2018b).

The same paragraph of the GCR also clarifies that development cooperation should be extended to middle-income host-countries, through “additional development resources, over and above regular development assistance, provided as grants or with a *high degree of concessionality* through both bilateral and multilateral channels” (UNGA, 2018b). Crucial to the distribution and adoption of these financial products is the fact that, through the GCR, they are presented as beneficial to both refugees and host countries and communities. This means that resources can be used for projects that also target the local community, for instance in terms of provision of health services, education and/or housing. Similarly, and importantly, development assistance is also prioritized to support countries of origin to “enable conditions for voluntary repatriation”, in line with current policy of deportation and expulsion to unsafe countries of origin disguised as “voluntary returns” (Bivand Erdal & Oeppen, 2018; Cassarino, 2020; Webber, 2011).

The provisions enshrined in the GCR have resulted into a cascade of humanitarian financial products and services designed “to unlock the potential of refugees” (Kluge et al., 2018) where the term “refugee” does not necessarily reflect existing international legal definitions and is rather understood as an umbrella term that includes refugees, migrants and internally displaced persons. It usually encompasses:

an inclusive group of people who are externally or internally forcibly displaced, whether through armed or political tension, ethnic tension, systematic discrimination, climate change or natural disaster, or the displacement of indigenous communities (Kluge et al., 2018).

Meanwhile, the well-meaning slogan of the CRRF aims at “helping refugees thrive, not just survive” and is premised on the fact that low and middle-income countries already shoulder much of the responsibility for refugees and that global responses to large-scale movements remain inadequate and underfunded, unable to ensure a more certain future for refugees. Aiming at early inclusion of refugees in the host communities, the CRRF conceives of refugee camps as an exception, to be resorted to only in emergency situations. The CRRF, therefore, has a

prevalent focus on access to education and labor markets, so that refugees can acquire skills, become self-reliant and contribute to the local economy and to the general development of the communities hosting them. The promotion of a “whole of society approach” to refugee responses at the heart of the CRRF sees as necessary the involvement of both development actors and private sector partners from the outset, to cover the humanitarian needs and objectives identified within the CRRF (see e.g. paragraph 6 CRRF above).

Crucially, however, the CRRF also marks a shift away from the traditional durable solutions recognized by UNHCR. Whilst seemingly acknowledging, at paragraph 9, that “millions of refugees around the world at present have no access to timely and durable solutions, the securing of which is one of the principal goals of international protection”, at paragraph 10 the CRRF calls for action toward a different set of durable solutions, namely “voluntary repatriation, *local solutions* and resettlement and *complementary pathways for admission*” (emphasis added). To confirm the distinction between local solution and local integration, paragraph 13 of the CRRF explains that host states commit to “provide legal stay to those seeking and in need of international protection as refugees, recognizing that any decision regarding permanent settlement in any form, including possible naturalization, rests with the host country.”

In terms of specific refugee rights, the same paragraph emphasizes a commitment to “take measures to foster self-reliance by pledging to expand opportunities for refugees to access, as appropriate, education, health care and services, livelihood opportunities and labor markets.” Long-term solutions are clearly linked to investment “in building human capital, self-reliance and transferable skills”, whilst paragraph 14(a) clearly refers to a commitment to “consider making available or expanding, including by encouraging private sector engagement and action as a supplementary measure, resettlement opportunities and complementary pathways for admission (e.g. medical evacuation, humanitarian admission, family reunification, opportunities for skilled migration, labor mobility and education).” Similarly, the UNHCR roadmap report mentioned earlier in this article (UNHCR, 2022c) clarifies the tight link between refugee finance and complementary pathways, and sets out to pursue innovative financing models to expand these programmes.

Once established the conceptual link between refugee finance and complementary pathways, as envisaged in the policy documents discussed so far, in the next section we focus on two case studies which help us flesh out the practical dimension of this new approach.

4. Contextualizing the shift “from funding to financing”: two specific case studies

In this section we examine two types of bonds which should be understood as design-stage grants. This means that they are allocated for the design or preparation of a project or intervention, to support for instance a feasibility study, a proof of concept or indeed a pilot. They provide the initial funding needed so that the project can later attract further investment. The aim is usually to improve the viability of a project that investors would otherwise consider too risky. A key feature of design-stage grants is that they are provided in advance with the specific aim of offering early-stage support during the design and structuring of the project’s activities. The two specific financial instruments examined in this section are rather new and have just been piloted or are still under implementation. Despite the paucity of data, it is possible to ascertain that both the targeted beneficiaries and the target for the realization of the bonds pivoted around the profile of a prototypical refugee, capable of quickly accessing the labor market (as with the KOTO social impact bond in Finland) or set up a “sustainable micro enterprise” (as with the Kois development impact bond in Jordan). This finding reinforces our suggestion that a new spectrum of refugeehood is delineating itself (spanning from the hyper vulnerable refugee to the refugee entrepreneur), with all the implications that this can potentially bring to the existing understanding of international protection.

4.1. The Kois development impact bond in Jordan

The investment firm Kois Invest, which specializes in asset management and financial services, designed a multi-country development impact bond aimed at funding employment integration interventions for Syrian refugees in areas such as vocational training, job placement, entrepreneurial support and language skills. The stated aim is to offer refugees a “sustainable future” in cooperation with neighboring countries. The initial funding was provided by a Convergence Design Funding Award (Convergence Global Network, 2016) which aimed to mobilize new sources of financing in order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals and catalyze the next generation of blended finance instruments. The focus is on easing participation in the labor market, a duty which usually “weighs heavily on the governments” of neighboring countries, and which is considered to foster long-term integration and provide refugees with a decent living (Feasibility Study, Convergence, 2017).

The main idea behind development impact bonds is to offer upfront funding for development programs by investors, who are remunerated by donors or host-country governments—and earn a return—if evidence shows that programs achieve pre-agreed social outcomes (Feasibility Study, Convergence, 2017). The proponents of such instruments argue that they address livelihood activities which “face significant funding gap” and the “need for long-term, results oriented funding that can contribute to the identification of successful intervention models” (Feasibility Study, Convergence, 2017).

The initial funding obtained by Kois Invest was used for a feasibility study, which aimed to analyze the potential design of the development impact bond for Syrian refugees and vulnerable populations in several countries in the Middle East, select host countries, complete preliminary due diligence of service providers and attract interested potential investors and outcome funders (Feasibility Study, Convergence, 2017). Jordan, Turkey and Lebanon were selected as host countries for the development impact bond on the basis of shortlisting criteria. Economic and political stability of the country were considered essential criteria in the selection process. According to Kois, political stability “impacts attitudes toward refugees and support from government” as well as the ability to sustain a multi-year program (Feasibility Study, Convergence, 2017) and economic stability is considered critical for any employment-focused intervention.

The second criterion focused on identifying countries with existing development activities which meant that it would be easier to find service providers and outcome funders. Political and public attitudes were considered relevant for the third criterion according to which the ideal host country was one that “has government and public buy-in for refugee integration and employment” (Feasibility Study, Convergence, 2017). This criterion was considered to be associated with easier access to work permits, healthcare and other social services, and social acceptance, which can increase the life standards of refugees by relieving pressure on government and service providers. Finally, the employment landscape of potential host countries for domestic populations and refugees was also assessed, including whether entrepreneurship is supported through legislation and availability of financing. Among the pre-agreed social outcomes was the number of individuals placed in employment and their income growth; the number of businesses started and sustained; and the growth in revenue/net income of the business (Feasibility Study, Convergence, 2017).

The development impact bond was launched in Jordan in 2021, and is yet to be followed by one in Lebanon (see further Koisinvest). The duration of the Jordan development impact bond is 4 years totaling 14 million USD with a 5.1% annual return rate (Kois Caring Finance Impact Report) or 20 million USD and a 6% internal rate of return with Lebanon included. The outcome funders are Ikea Foundation, Novo Nordisk Foundation and Norad, and the borrower of the development impact bond is the Near East Foundation (NEF), which has expertise in microenterprise training and grants programme (Kois Caring Finance Impact Report). Under this development impact bond, local populations and refugees will represent respectively 70% and 30% of the beneficiaries (Kois Caring Finance Impact Report) with activities revolving

around the provision of skills building, vocational training, business development, market facilitation, and startup grants. These in turns aim at the development and growth of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises and new income generating activities (Kois Caring Finance Impact Report).

To support this development impact bond, investors have committed to contribute ~\$10 million upfront toward the delivery by NEF of its programme (Kois Caring Finance Impact Report) and they will recoup 80% to 100% of their capital, plus a potential return, based on the level of achievement of impact targets. The expected impact is to have 2560 sustainable micro-enterprises created in Jordan (Refugee Impact Bond). At the time of writing there is no publicly available data on the results achieved since the start of the pilot. Despite the employment of shortlisting criteria to select non-European low and middle-income countries that host refugees in the region of origin, research points to a continuous inability to provide access to permanent solutions because of the high costs involved (Davitti & Vankova, 2024). The implementation of the Jordan Compact is a case in point. It exemplifies how refugee finance instruments provided by the EU in cooperation with the World Bank to achieve “protection” and containment goals through financing (Gordon, 2019), in practice failed in providing *durable* protection for those whom it assisted (Lenner & Turner, 2019).

4.2. The Kotouttamisen (KOTO) social impact bond in Finland

As part of the response to the increase in refugees’ arrivals in 2015, in 2017 the Finnish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment issued the nation-wide KOTO social impact bond for a period of three years to enable market access for recently arrived forced migrants through tailored vocational and language training (Government Outcomes Lab (GOLAB) Knowledge Bank, 2022), after an initial pilot in 2016. This labor market access project, run through a social impact bond, was described as “a form of social outcomes contracting in which a private partner provides financing and takes on the performance risk. With social impact bond contracting, the public body pays only when certain performance outcomes are achieved. In this case, the performance indicators were based on reduced need for unemployment payments and increased tax revenue from the employment of participants in the programme” (Ministry of Economic Affairs & Employment & Finland, 2020). The impact of the KOTO social impact bond on each individual was tracked through the participants’ identification numbers, with the Social Insurance Institution in Finland (Kela) monitoring the data on unemployment benefits, and the Finnish Tax Administration monitoring the data on income tax.

Crucially this was one of the first social impact projects of this kind to be implemented in Europe and was co-financed by the European Investment Fund, the European Fund for Strategic Investments and the European Commission, together with private and institutional investors (ibid). Aggregate data show that EUR 14.2m were raised from investors, with the European Investment Fund being a catalytic investor, providing 71% of the total investment, and providing significance knowledge and expertise in terms of fund structuring and governance (European Investment Advisory Hub, 2021). Given the level of co-financing, it is fair to question the eventual scalability of such a financial mechanism, though it is not clear, at this stage, whether reproduction on a larger scale was ever one of the initial objectives.

The targeted beneficiaries of this social impact bond were immigrants aged between 17 and 63 who had been granted a residence permit on the basis of international protection and who had registered as unemployed job seekers at the Finnish Employment and Economic Development Office (GOLAB, 2022). In order to be included in a random referral process, the participants also had to be able to read and write using the Latin alphabet, as well as willing to learn Finnish and work in Finland (European Investment Advisory Hub, 2021). A key element of this financial instrument, which in turn also shows a potential alignment with complementary pathways, is the link between vocational training and shortages in the Finnish job market. The Finnish Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Employment selected Equipus Ltd, and later FIM Impact Investing

Ltd, as the programme/fund manager to implement the programme and setting up the fund in which the European Investment Fund and other investors were then able to invest. The initial target for the social impact bond was the inclusion of 2500 participants in the job markets over three years. According to a report by the European Investment Advisory Hub's Social Outcomes Contracting Advisory Platform of the European Investment Bank, 2217 people participated in the programme. 1692 participants received training for at least 70 days, and 1062 were in employment by the end of 2020 (European Investment Advisory Hub, 2021). The 50% success rate of the KOTO social impact bond was presented by the Finnish government as “win-win-win” for the host state, the refugee and the investor (FI Compass, 2022). The final external evaluation of the programme, however, was yet to be published at the moment of writing. The KOTO social impact bond has currently been replaced by the Tie Takaisin Työelämään social impact bond which is a broader performance-based employment programme targeting those in long-term unemployment for the period 2020-2025 (Työ SIB, 2024).

5. Conclusion

In this article we have examined the co-emergence of policies aimed at establishing complementary pathways to international protection and at setting up refugee financial mechanisms for refugee responses, the latter a phenomenon also known as refugee finance. We have seen that both sets of policies are anchored in the implementation of the CRRF and the GCR, as part of efforts clearly encouraging refugees' resilience and self-reliance whilst also creating a conducive environment for sustainable investment. The hypothesis set out at the beginning of this article is that the strengthening of international protection cannot be automatically assumed from an increased reliance on refugee finance and complementary pathways and that these policies, if left unscrutinized, may be (mis)used as additional migration control tools. There is a clear risk that these policies, framed within the CRRF's objectives of encouraging third-country solutions and supporting refugees' self-reliance, could become key tools for entrenching the containment and externalization of migration, exacerbating already existing trends toward temporary solutions which prioritized *local* rather than *durable* protection. Increased reliance on complementary pathways is already starting to alter the protection space and, when examined in conjunction with refugee finance, the risk that these policies may create a new spectrum of refugeehood is apparent, with the “hyper vulnerable” refugee on one end of the spectrum and the “refugee entrepreneur” on the other. The former represents the only category of refugees still eligible for resettlement, whilst the latter epitomizes the “ideal” refugees, with the potential of becoming a business owner or a migrant worker or a student in order to access the new complementary pathways made available to them. In the shrinking middle part of this new spectrum of refugeehood, we have identified spontaneous refugees who do not meet the requirements of hyper-vulnerability or entrepreneurship and for whom, therefore, access to protection is becoming increasingly difficult.

We have tested our hypothesis by extending our analysis to two financial instruments: a development impact bond in Jordan for Syrian refugees, the Kois bond, and a social impact bond for the integration of refugees in the Finnish labor market, the KOTO bond. As we have seen in our analysis, at the core of the protection interventions funded by these financial instruments, there are activities aimed at the provision of skills building, vocational training, business development, market facilitation, and startup grants. They are both aimed at a prototypical idea of a refugee, as a person who is able to contribute and to offer skills. Relatedly, it is therefore only fair to question who are ultimately the refugees that the international legal system *can* indeed “protect” when protection measures are reoriented toward an increased dependence upon private investors who become key enablers and co-providers of “protection.” There is little doubt that both complementary pathways and refugee finance have the potential to provide solutions for some of current refugee challenges and the calls for expanding and strengthening refugee finance are rapidly increasing. Yet, these questions remain so far unanswered and only time will

tell how refugee finance will impact the trajectory of international protection measures currently deployed at EU level and beyond (European Research Council Starting Grant, 2023).

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